

Scaling up bioinformatics with ABLeS

The Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

ABLES team

- **Dr. Ziad Al Bkhetan**, Bioinformatics Application Specialist, Australian BioCommons
- **Dr. Johan Gustafsson**, Bioinformatics Engagement Officer, Australian BioCommons
- **Dr. Steven Manos**, A/Director - BioCloud, Australian BioCommons

Speakers from ABLeS community

- **Dr. Hardip Patel**, National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, John Curtin School of Medical Research, Australian National University.
- **Chelsea Mayoh**, Zero Childhood Cancer, Children's Cancer Institute
- **Theodore Allnutt**, Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria

Infrastructure supporting omics use in life science

Australian Government

National Research
Infrastructure for Australia

An Australian Government Initiative

BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA

Est. 2007

Mission: to provide access to 'omics technologies in support of all Australian life science researchers working across human health, agriculture, biodiversity and industry.

Infrastructure supporting omics use in life science

Australian Government

**BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA**

Est. 2007

Mission: to provide access to 'omics technologies in support of all Australian life science researchers working across human health, agriculture, biodiversity and industry.

**Australian
BioCommons**

Est. 2019

Mission: To actively support Australian life science research communities with bioinformatics and bioscience data infrastructures at a national scale.

The Australian BioCommons

facilitate interactions with computational providers to build a more fit-for-purpose, flexible and cohesive data analysis ecosystem

We identify what life science research communities need

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

core facilities

bioinformaticians

life scientists

Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia
V4.0
Dec 2022

Genome Assembly Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia
V4.0
July 2020

Comparative Genomics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia
V4.0
September 2022

We identify what life science research communities need

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

Deploy

We identify what life science research communities need

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

Deploy

Cross-cutting themes leading to ABLeS

Bioinformatics compute use
is episodic in nature

Multi-year time frames,
dependent on collaborations

Compute use is primarily
driven by data availability

Biology is complex, unpredictable and
does not respect time tables

Software is diverse

Imported, complex, rapidly evolving,
multi-language and not optimised for HPC

Various types of expertise
and effective coordination
are needed

Community that promotes, supports and
coordinates collaborative effort, and which can
onboard less experienced RSEs

Researcher requirements

Easy access to
compute
infrastructure

Long term
access

Easily
accessible tools
and pipelines

Documentation
and support

Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

ABLES support

pawsey

NCI
AUSTRALIA

Infrastructure

**Shared repository of
tools and workflows**

Expertise

Australian
BioCommons

ABLeS compute resources

Resource	ABLeS scheme					
	Reference data		Production bioinformatics		Software accelerator	
	NCI	Pawsey	NCI	Pawsey	NCI	Pawsey
Compute infrastructure	HPC and cloud					
Temporary storage ¹⁹	5 TB	1 PB	5 TB	1 PB	1 TB	1 PB
Project storage ²⁰	5 TB		5 TB		1 TB	
Default service units ²¹	100 kSUs per Quarter		50 kSUs per Quarter		10 kSUs per Quarter	
Time frame	Ongoing				6-12 months	
Specialist support	Yes					
Additional resources	Yes				Yes if the previous usage is > 60%	

ABLeS expectations

Generate outcomes that benefit the broader bioinformatics communities

Project leadership

Community level expertise

**Appropriate use of the
resources**

Supporting ABLeS growth

**Follow compute facility access
policies**

**Citing and acknowledging
ABLeS**

ABLeS Today

24

Number of ABLeS participants

148

Number of registered ABLeS users

25

Number of universities accessing ABLeS

121

Number of tools installed

6,500

kSU available per quarter

112

TB storage being provided to participants

ABLES users

Australian Genome Research Facility	Garvan Institute of Medical Research	Queensland University of Technology (QUT)	Australian Wine Research Institute
Australian National University	James Cook University	Southern Cross University	University of Queensland
Children's Cancer Institute	La Trobe University	St Vincent's Institute of Medical Research	University of Sydney
City of Hope	Macquarie University	Telethon Kids Institute	University of the Sunshine Coast
Department of Biodiversity - Conservation and Attractions	National Institute of Biological Sciences, Beijing	Royal Botanic Garden - Sydney	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
CSIRO	National Computational Infrastructure	Royal Botanic Garden - Victoria	University of Western Australia
Department of Natural Resources and Environment Tasmania	Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre	University of Adelaide	University of New England
Flinders University	University of Melbourne	University of Canberra	University of Wollongong
University of New South Wales	Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute	WEHI	

ABLES - Use cases

- **Australian amphibian and reptile genomics**

Dr. Hardip Patel, National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, John Curtin School of Medical Research, Australian National University.

- **Zero Childhood Project**

Chelsea Mayoh, Zero Childhood Cancer, Children's Cancer Institute

- **Genomics for Australian Plants**

Theodore Allnutt, Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria

More information

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/ables>

<https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/>

The Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS)

Quick access links

- Request New Project
- Request Additional Resources
- Request Software Installation
- Request Help
- Report Project Outcome
- Available Tools

About ABLeS

The ABLeS (Australian BioCommons Leadership Share) program was established in April 2021 to more readily support data-driven bioinformatics. This effort is supported by the Australian BioCommons in partnership with BigPlatforms Australia, the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI), Caribena, and the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre (Pawsey, PetaN).

ABLeS targets established groups and communities that are focused on a common research theme, create reference data and/or software, and have the ability to plan and prioritise a computational research program.

ABLeS projects broadly align with the following three principles:

1. They are life science related and are producing and sharing data, research, or software centric outcomes.
2. The project users have expertise which will drive and execute its bioinformatics agenda of the project.
3. Resources are planned and approached with a level of care appropriate to their status as limited and consumable resources.

The support available includes access to computational and data infrastructure, specialist expertise, support to adopt best practices and share outputs effectively, and a community led and shared repository of bioinformatics software (i.e. tools and workflow).

More details are available in the ABLeS publication

Gustafson, Ove Johan Ragnar, Al Biberian, Ziad, Francis, Rhys & Mawoo, Steven. (2022). Enabling national step changes in bioinformatics through ABLeS: the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1012901>

ABLeS project types

Creation of reference data assets

ABLeS reference data allocations support research groups and consortia within the life sciences to access the dedicated compute capacity required to efficiently construct reference data.

Production bioinformatics

